

Example of a Business Process with Three Process Variants

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Abstract. This document contains the mockups related to a business process with three process variants. Such mockups have been designed to be used for generating user interface event logs in the context of robotic process automation.

1 BPMN of the example

We consider a business process with three process variants (cf. Figure 1): (1) the client requests unsubscription, and after checking that she is up to date with payments, the required unsubscription is performed (the client is notified by e-mail), (2) the client requests unsubscription, and after checking that she is not up to date with payments, the required unsubscription is not performed (the client is notified by e-mail), and (3) the client requests billing information related to her last payment receipt, and this receipt is sent to her by e-mail.

In this example, there are $n : m$ relations between *screenIds* and business activities, as can be observed in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Example of a business process with three process variants.

Fig. 2. n:m relation between business activities and screen IDs in the running example.

2 Mockups

As can be observed, each mockup is related to only one *screenId* while there are may be several mockups related to the same *screenId*.

Fig. 3. S1M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 4. S1M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 5. S1M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 6. S1M4: Mockup M4 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 7. S1M5: Mockup M5 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 8. S1M6: Mockup M6 Related to screen S1.

Fig. 9. S2M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S2.

Fig. 10. S2M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S2.

Fig. 11. S2M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S2.

Fig. 12. S2M4: Mockup M4 Related to screen S2.

Fig. 13. S3M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S3.

Fig. 14. S3M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S3.

Fig. 15. S3M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S3.

Fig. 16. S3M4: Mockup M4 Related to screen S3.

Fig. 17. S4M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S4.

Fig. 18. S4M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S4.

Fig. 19. S5M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S5.

Fig. 20. S6M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S6.

Fig. 21. S6M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S6.

Fig. 22. S7M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S7.

Fig. 23. S8M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 24. S8M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 25. S8M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 26. S8M4: Mockup M4 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 27. S8M5: Mockup M5 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 28. S8M6: Mockup M6 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 29. S8M7: Mockup M7 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 30. S8M8: Mockup M8 Related to screen S8.

Fig. 31. S9M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S9.

Fig. 32. S9M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S9.

Fig. 33. S9M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S9.

Fig. 34. S10M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S10.

Fig. 35. S11M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S11.

Fig. 36. S11M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S11.

Fig. 37. S11M3: Mockup M3 Related to screen S11.

Fig. 38. S12M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S12.

Fig. 39. S13M1: Mockup M1 Related to screen S13.

Fig. 40. S13M2: Mockup M2 Related to screen S13.